

1 **TITLE: Macroinvertebrate functional diversity as a tool to evaluate wetland**
2 **restoration efficacy**

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28 ABSTRACT

29 1. Ecological restoration of aquatic ecosystems has become widespread in recent
30 decades. Whereas the recovery of biodiversity in restored wetlands has been studied
31 from a taxonomic perspective, our knowledge of how functional biodiversity
32 recovers remains poorly understood.

33 2. We studied the functional diversity of macroinvertebrate communities in 32
34 Mediterranean temporary ponds six to seven years after their creation during a
35 restoration in South-West Spain, and compared them with 10 natural reference sites
36 during two consecutive hydroperiods. We compared alpha functional diversity
37 indices, and the individual contributions of new ponds and reference sites to the
38 regional functional beta diversity, as well as to its turnover and nestedness
39 components. We also investigated the influence of environmental and spatial
40 variables on the dissimilarities of functional beta diversity and its components
41 between new ponds and reference sites.

42 3. Alpha functional diversity in new ponds was lower than in reference sites, but the
43 contribution of new ponds to the regional functional beta diversity was similar to
44 that of reference sites. Reference sites contributed more to functional turnover,
45 while new ponds contributed more to functional nestedness.

46 4. Dispersal limitation coupled with environmental filtering structured the functional
47 variations in communities between new ponds and reference sites, but their relative
48 importance differed between beta components. New ponds can hold species with
49 unique functional compositions, but their contribution to the regional functional
50 beta diversity was mostly due to trait losses with respect to reference sites.

51 5. *Synthesis and applications.* We showed that considering different aspects of
52 functional diversity can help elucidate the processes and mechanisms through

53 which ecosystems recover following restoration. We encourage use of trait-based
54 approaches to reveal general trends in process and patterns that can guide future
55 restoration projects in wetlands.

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57 **KEYWORDS:** functional beta diversity, macroinvertebrate, Mediterranean, nestedness,
58 restoration, turnover

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82 INTRODUCTION

83 Wetlands are critical ecosystems for sustaining biodiversity and ecosystem services to humans
84 (Maltby & Acreman, 2011). Nonetheless, wetland loss and degradation continue to be a
85 global problem. Mediterranean wetlands are particularly at risk, being threatened by e.g., land
86 use change, water overexploitation or climate change (Taylor et al., 2021). In recent decades,
87 ecological restoration of aquatic ecosystems has become widespread in effort to reverse these
88 losses, and is expected to increase during the current decade (Bregnballe et al., 2014; Arias
89 García & Gómez Zotano, 2015). Integrative freshwater ecology and biodiversity conservation
90 approaches are needed in wetland management (Geist, 2011). This requires understanding
91 functional diversity of biological communities in these systems in order to make conservation
92 and restoration evidence-based and effective (Geist, 2015; Geist & Hawkins, 2016). However,
93 the outcomes of wetland restorations in many cases remain unclear (Zedler et al., 2007).

94 In general, restoration success focuses on the recovery of taxonomic biodiversity
95 compared with reference sites, which in many cases has been slow and incomplete (Moreno-
96 Mateos et al., 2012). Nevertheless, biodiversity includes other dimensions e.g. phylogenetic
97 and functional diversity, which can provide complementary insights (Perez-Rocha et al.,
98 2018). Functional diversity represents the variety of morphological, physiological and
99 phenological measurable traits (e.g. body size; life history characteristic; feeding habits)
100 within communities. Since functional traits determine the response of organisms to
101 environmental changes and their effects on the system, linking biodiversity, ecosystem
102 functioning and environmental constraints, they are ideal for assessing the effects of
103 restoration (Cadotte et al., 2011; Montoya et al., 2012). Nonetheless, functional diversity and
104 its components have only rarely been considered to assess restoration success, mainly
105 focusing on changes in alpha functional diversity through restoration (Español et al., 2015;
106 Rumm et al., 2018).

107 Functional diversity can be described by its alpha (functional trait variation within an
108 individual site [local]) and beta (functional variations between sites) components (Whittaker,
109 1960). Moreover, the beta component can also be partitioned into its nestedness (differences
110 in trait richness between sites) and turnover (trait replacement between sites) subcomponents
111 (Baselga, 2010; Villéger et al., 2013). Patterns of alpha and beta functional diversity can be
112 used to infer the ecological processes structuring community re-assembly during restoration,
113 such as environmental filtering, dispersal limitation and competition, as well as community
114 effects on ecosystem functioning (Feit et al., 2019).

115 In general, newly created habitats have unoccupied niches that are quickly colonized
116 by some pioneer macroinvertebrate species from nearby natural wetlands (Bloechl et al.,
117 2010). These colonizers possess traits that allow them to use a wide range of resources,
118 disperse over long distances and reproduce quickly (i.e. short life cycle). As time after
119 restoration increases, and in relation to increases in niche availability through time, generalist
120 species are gradually replaced by specialists with narrower environmental tolerance, limited
121 dispersal capacity and longer life cycles (Ruhí et al., 2013). In restored wetlands, pioneering
122 communities dominated by active dispersers usually represent a nested subset of species
123 present in older natural wetlands (Ruhí et al., 2013).

124 Aquatic macroinvertebrates participate in and regulate key ecological functions such
125 as nutrient cycling and primary production (Batzer & Wissinger, 1996; Schmera et al., 2017).
126 Macroinvertebrates are sensitive to ecological conditions, including habitat heterogeneity
127 (Heino et al., 2003) and water quality (Soldner et al., 2004). In addition, they possess a broad
128 range of functional traits, making them excellent models for functional-based studies.

129 Here, we evaluate the success of Mediterranean temporary ponds created during
130 wetland restoration in supporting macroinvertebrate functional diversity. First, we compared
131 alpha functional diversity between new ponds and reference sites during two consecutive

132 hydroperiods. Second, we compared the contributions of new ponds and reference sites to the
133 overall regional functional beta diversity and to its turnover and nestedness components, as
134 well as the differences in the levels of beta diversity (and its components) within each wetland
135 type. Finally, we investigated the influence of environmental and spatial variables on the
136 functional beta diversity (and its components) calculated between new ponds and reference
137 sites. Examining both functional alpha and beta diversity components may help to understand
138 the outcomes of restoration at the local scale, and the processes that affect the restoration at
139 the landscape level.

140 In a previous study of the same system, Coccia et al. (2016) showed that taxonomic
141 diversity in new ponds matched or was even higher than that of reference sites, while their
142 habitat heterogeneity was lower. Nonetheless, we expected that i) alpha functional diversity
143 would be higher in reference sites than in new ponds, because their greater environmental
144 heterogeneity may enable more varied trait compositions (Wilson, 1999). We also expected ii)
145 to observe differences in the contribution to the overall regional functional beta diversity and
146 its components (nestedness and turnover) between new ponds and reference sites, because
147 they should be influenced by differences in habitat heterogeneity and by dispersal limitation.
148 Specifically, we expected that reference sites would contribute more to overall functional
149 turnover because they support species that have less dispersal capacity and/or greater
150 specialization to specific habitats. In contrast, new ponds should show strong functional
151 nestedness because they support pioneering communities (Coccia et al., 2016). Finally, based
152 on other studies conducted on aquatic macroinvertebrates (Español et al., 2015; Hill et al.,
153 2019), we expected that iii) the environmental differences between new ponds and reference
154 sites would drive functional beta diversity and its components, because traits should reflect
155 adaptations to the environment.

156

157 METHODS

158 *Study area and climate*

159 This study was conducted within and around the Caracoles estate, at the northern edge of
160 Doñana National Park (Southwest Spain) (Fig. 1). This estate of 27 Km² was a former
161 seasonally inundated marsh that was disconnected from the surrounding marshes and turned
162 into arable farmland during the 1960s. During 2004-2005, due to a restoration plan aimed at
163 reestablishing former connectivity with surrounding marshes, the agricultural drainage system
164 was removed and a set of 96 elliptically-shaped temporary ponds were created. The ponds
165 were of three different sizes (with a long axis of 250, 125 and 60 m in 8, 24 and 64 ponds,
166 respectively) and two excavation depths (30 and 60 cm). These ponds are distributed in two
167 main blocks of 44 ponds each, plus 8 medium size, relatively isolated ponds distributed
168 throughout the estate (Fig. 1). The ponds are filled mainly by local precipitation, with
169 important variation in water level according to season and year, occasionally overflowing and
170 connecting after major rainfall events, and drying out completely during summer (Coccia et
171 al., 2016). The colonization of these ponds by waterbirds, zooplankton and
172 macroinvertebrates has been previously described (Frisch et al., 2012; Sebastián-González &
173 Green, 2014; Coccia et al., 2016).

174 Doñana has a Mediterranean climate with Atlantic influence, determined by short,
175 mild winters and dry, hot summers. Rainfall is variable and concentrated mainly between
176 October and the beginning of April (wet season), with little precipitation and high
177 temperatures causing rapid evaporation from April to September (dry season) (Paredes et al.
178 2021). Caracoles ponds and surrounding water-bodies are usually flooded during the wet
179 season and dry out in summer (Coccia et al., 2016). Dates of flooding and drying vary among
180 years, as a result of different rainfall and evaporation patterns, which are quantified for
181 hydrological years running from September to the following August. Total precipitation was

182 784 mm during the first study hydroperiod (between 2009-2010) and 712 mm for the second
183 (2010-2011) (Coccia et al., 2016).

184

185 *Study site characterization*

186 We selected 32 new ponds in Caracoles representing all size and depth classes (Fig. 1, Table
187 S1), including 24 within the two blocks and the 8 outside. In addition, we also sampled 10
188 nearby older, temporary, shallow waterbodies as reference sites (Fig. 1, Table S1). These
189 reference sites are similar to new ponds as they fill in response to rainfall and dry out during
190 the dry summers. Occasionally, heavy flooding in the marshes can connect almost the whole
191 area for several days, including some connections between new ponds and reference sites, as
192 occurred during our two study hydroperiods (Coccia et al., 2016). Choice of reference sites
193 was limited because the Caracoles estate is surrounded by drained farmland to the North and
194 East, and a continuous and inaccessible marshland to the south and west. Owing to limited
195 options for reference sites, they included a greater range in size and depth than the new ponds.
196 However, this combination of new ponds and reference sites has previously been shown to be
197 an adequate system to study restoration trajectories (Frisch et al., 2012; Coccia et al., 2016).

198

199 *Environmental and taxonomic data*

200 Environmental and taxonomic data were collected in May, the month with the most extensive
201 sampling during both hydroperiods (2009-2010 and 2010-2011, from Coccia et al., 2016). We
202 excluded taxa for which taxonomic identification did not reach the family level (e.g.,
203 Nematoda and Oligochaeta). The final data set included 70 taxa belonging to 19 families and
204 51 genera (Table S2); plus 10 environmental and 2 spatial variables (Table S3).
205 Previous analyses in Coccia et al. (2016) found significant differences between new ponds
206 and reference sites in some environmental variables, including pH, chlorophyll-a

207 concentration, vegetation cover, and fish (see Moreno-Valcarcel et al., 2013 for details of
208 fish) (Table S4).

209

210 *Functional traits*

211 For the characterization of macroinvertebrates, we selected 14 functional traits related either
212 to morphology, physiology or behavior. These included: Maximal potential body length, Life
213 cycle duration, Potential number of cycles per year, Aquatic stages, Dispersal, Resistance
214 forms, Locomotion and substrate relation, Food preference, Feeding habits, Adult life span,
215 Female wing length, Wing pair type, Lifelong fecundity, and Propensity to drift. These traits
216 were selected because they describe the influence of macroinvertebrates on ecosystem
217 processes, such as on nutrient cycling, secondary productivity and energetic transfer (see
218 Table S5 for details on the relationships between each trait and functions). The affinity values
219 of genera with the different trait categories were determined mainly using Tachet et al. (2002)
220 and Sarremejane et al. (2020), but see Table S6 for exceptions. Affinity values at the family
221 level were estimated as the average of affinity values of all the genera in that family
222 (Sarremejane et al., 2017). If values for genera belonging to a family in our data set were
223 undescribed, we used affinity values for other genera from that family covered by the above
224 references.

225

226 *Functional diversity*

227 We calculated alpha and beta functional diversity for each wetland type (i.e. new ponds or
228 reference sites) in each sampled year. As software limitations prevent beta functional
229 measurements to be calculated considering species abundances, we considered only presence-
230 absence data in the calculation of both alpha and beta diversities. As measurements of alpha
231 diversity, we calculated complementary functional diversity indices that together describe the

232 community functional structure, i.e. the distribution of species in the functional space built
233 from trait values. We constructed the functional space by computing a principal coordinates
234 analysis (PCoA; Gower, 1966) from trait values of all taxa present in our samples. First, we
235 calculated functional distances among pairs of taxa using the Gower distance (Gower, 1966).
236 Then, we performed a PCoA on the functional distance matrix and considered the PCoA axes
237 as dimensions of the functional space. We removed sites with four or less taxa from all
238 analyses so that we could use at least four axes to construct functional space. A total of three
239 new ponds (2 in 2010 and 1 in 2011) and 1 reference site (2011) were removed.

240 From the scores of the taxa in the axes, we calculated functional richness (FRic),
241 functional evenness (FEve), functional divergence (FDiv) and functional dispersion (FDis)
242 (Laliberté & Legendre, 2010). FRic is the volume of the minimum convex hull of the
243 community, where taxa with more extreme functional trait values are the vertices of the hull
244 (Fig. 2A). It represents the volume of the functional space occupied by each community, and
245 varies when the composition of taxa with extreme traits changes. FEve is the minimum
246 spanning tree among taxa, and describes how evenly taxa are distributed in the functional
247 space, increasing when functional distances among them are more regular (Fig. 2B). FDiv is
248 the mean distance of all taxa present in a community to its center of gravity. It represents the
249 degree to which taxa are distributed towards the edges of the occupied functional volume, and
250 increases when taxa in a community are more dissimilar (Fig. 2C). Finally, FDis is the mean
251 distance of taxa to the centroid of the community, and increases when taxa are more dispersed
252 in the overall functional space (Fig. 2D). To evaluate if there were differences in values of
253 specific functional traits between new ponds and reference sites, we evaluated Community
254 Weighted Means (CWM, Garnier et al., 2004) of each trait category. CWM is a community-
255 level mean of the values that each taxon has for a given trait. First, we calculated CWMs for
256 each trait category in each wetland type. Then, we correlated these values with the site scores

257 in the four PCoA axes, to identify which traits were more responsible for the distribution of
258 species in the functional space (considered to be those with $r > 0.6$). We calculated all indices
259 with the dbFD function of the 'FD' package (Laliberté & Legendre, 2010; Laliberté et al.,
260 2014) within the R environment, v. 3.5.1 (R Core Team, 2018).

261 We calculated functional pairwise beta diversity among all wetland types, and its
262 turnover and nestedness components (Baselga, 2010; Villéger et al., 2011). We calculated
263 total functional beta diversity as the Sorensen dissimilarity index, representing total variation
264 among communities. The turnover component (dissimilarity due to the replacement of some
265 traits by others) was calculated as the Simpson dissimilarity index. Finally, the nestedness
266 component (dissimilarity due to differences in functional richness among communities) was
267 quantified as the difference between total beta diversity and its turnover component. For each
268 year, we generated a dissimilarity matrix for each of these components of beta. Then, we used
269 these distance matrices in multivariate dispersion analyses (Anderson, 2006) in two ways: 1)
270 to compare the contributions of new ponds and reference sites to overall (regional) beta
271 diversity, we obtained distances of each wetland type to the median of all wetland types
272 (combining both new ponds and reference sites) in the multivariate space (Fig. 2E). Then, 2)
273 to evaluate differences in beta diversity and its components when they were calculated
274 separately for each wetland type, we obtained distances of each wetland to the median of all
275 sites of that type (i.e., one median for new ponds, another median for reference sites, Fig. 2F).
276 We calculated pairwise functional beta diversity with the functional.beta.pair function of the
277 'betapart' package (Baselga et al., 2017), and performed multivariate dispersion analyses with
278 the function betadisper of the 'vegan' package (Oksanen et al., 2018), in the R environment,
279 v. 3.5.1 (R Core Team, 2018).

280

281 *Data analyses*

282 To evaluate differences in functional alpha diversity between wetland types, we fitted linear
283 mixed models (LMM) to the values of each functional diversity index (FRic, FEve, FDiv,
284 FDis and CWMs highly correlated with PCoA axes) using wetland type as an explanatory
285 variable and year as a random factor. We compared those models to null models constructed
286 without the variable “wetland type” and selected the model with lower Δ AIC in each case. To
287 evaluate differences in the contribution of each wetland type to regional beta diversity (and its
288 turnover and nestedness components), we fitted linear models to the distances for each
289 individual wetland from the median for all sites generated by multivariate dispersion analyses,
290 separately for each year. We checked assumptions for all models graphically. Models were
291 fitted using the lmer and lm functions (package ‘lme4’, Bates et al., 2015), in the R
292 environment v. 3.5.1 (R Core Team, 2018).

293 To evaluate differences in the levels of beta diversity among new ponds and among
294 reference sites, we used a permutation-based test of multivariate homogeneity of group
295 dispersions on the results from betadisper when calculated with medians for each group. This
296 was done using the permutest function from the ‘vegan’ package, in R, correcting for unequal
297 number of samples between wetland types.

298 We also evaluated how environmental variables influenced dissimilarity among
299 wetland types in beta diversity. In Mediterranean wetlands, most environmental variables
300 (e.g. flooding area, depth) vary between years, so we analyzed each year separately. To
301 identify which connectivity and environmental variables were the best predictors of
302 differences between new ponds and reference sites in regional functional beta diversity,
303 turnover and nestedness, we used Generalized Dissimilarity Modelling (GDM; Ferrier et al.,
304 2007). We calculated GDMs for each beta diversity index in each year, using the dissimilarity
305 matrices generated by the functional.beta.pair function as a response variable, and a matrix of
306 environmental variables and geographical distances among wetland types as explanatory

307 variables. In order to account only for the differences between wetland types, we only used
308 the pairwise dissimilarities between reference sites and new ponds, removing new pond x new
309 pond and reference site x reference site dissimilarities in the following steps. GDM makes no
310 assumptions about the shape of distributions, and it assumes only that the relationship
311 between variables increases (or decreases) monotonically. We used the default setting of three
312 I-splines to define the flexibility of the fit. We started GDM fitting with all the available
313 variables. Then, we followed a permutation-based backward elimination procedure (Ferrier et
314 al., 2007). In each step of this procedure, all environmental variables included in the model
315 were permuted in turn, and the difference in explained deviance between the permuted model
316 and the previous one was calculated. After 999 permutations, the variable with the least
317 significant contribution to explained deviance was excluded. This procedure was repeated
318 until all variables included in the model made significant contributions to explained deviance
319 ($p < 0.05$). We fitted GDMs using the functions `gdm` and `gdm.varImp` from the ‘`gdm`’ package
320 (Fitzpatrick et al., 2020), in the R environment, v. 3.5.1 (R Core Team, 2018).

321

322 RESULTS

323 *Alpha diversity*

324 Linear Mixed Models (LMMs) indicated differences in alpha functional diversity indices
325 between reference sites and new ponds while controlling for year. Specifically, reference sites
326 had higher Functional Richness (FRic) and Functional Dispersion (FDis) compared to new
327 ponds (Fig. 3, Table S7). We found ten functional trait categories with CWM correlations to
328 PCoA axes > 0.6 (Table S8). Among these, new ponds showed higher CWMs than reference
329 sites for “aerial active” (within the Dispersal trait), “flier” (Locomotion and Substrate
330 Relation trait), and “one pair of wings plus one pair of elytra/pseudoelytra” (Wing Pair Type

331 trait) (Fig. 4, Table S9). Reference sites showed higher CWMs for “predators” (Feeding Habit
332 trait), “no wings”, and “two pairs of wings” (Wing Pair Types trait) (Fig. 4, Table S9).

333

334 *Beta diversity*

335 Differences in the contribution to regional functional turnover and nestedness between
336 wetland types varied between years (Fig. 5, Table S10). In both years, reference sites
337 contributed more than new ponds to functional turnover, while in 2011 new ponds contributed
338 more than reference sites to functional nestedness. The permutation test of multivariate
339 homogeneity of group dispersions showed no significant differences in the level of beta
340 diversity (intra-group differences) or its components between new ponds and reference sites
341 (Fig. 6, Table S11). However, multivariate dispersion analyses showed a clear separation
342 between reference sites and new ponds for total beta diversity and turnover in 2011 (Fig. 6).

343 GDM models showed that dissimilarities between wetland types in regional functional
344 beta diversity, turnover and nestedness depended on different variables each year (Fig. 7,
345 Table 1). In 2010, no significant variables were found to affect total beta diversity and
346 turnover, while nestedness increased steadily with emergent vegetation cover and values of
347 total nitrogen > 1.5 ppm (Fig. 7). During 2011, total beta diversity increased with geographic
348 distance and with values of turbidity above 60 NTU; turnover increased with geographic
349 distance until around 0.025 decimal degrees, distance to the nearest pond, distance to the
350 nearest reference site (especially in the first 1000 m) and fish presence; and nestedness
351 increased with pH, plateauing around a pH value of nine (Fig. 7).

352

353 DISCUSSION

354 We used a trait-based approach to evaluate the efficacy of wetland restoration in supporting
355 macroinvertebrate functional diversity in South-West Spain. Functional traits have been used

356 previously to measure restoration success in other aquatic systems and taxa (Español et al.,
357 2015; Josué et al., 2021), but in our unique study of a Mediterranean restoration we
358 partitioned total functional beta diversity into its turnover and nestedness components, and
359 explored how environmental and spatial variables affected the dissimilarities of the restored
360 area. We found some aspects of alpha functional diversity were still lower in new ponds than
361 in reference sites 6 six to seven years after restoration, and a prevalence of functional beta
362 nestedness in new ponds across the wetland area. We also revealed that functional diversity
363 patterns were structured by both dispersal based processes (through trait replacements) and
364 environmental filtering (through trait losses).

365

366 *Differences in functional alpha diversity between new ponds and reference sites*

367 Macroinvertebrates in new ponds showed lower functional richness (FRic) and dispersion
368 (FDis) than in reference sites. Functional alpha diversity tends to be related to species
369 richness (i.e. higher functional diversity in taxonomic richer sites, see Mason et al., 2005), but
370 taxonomic diversity in new ponds matched, or was even higher than for reference sites
371 (Coccia et al., 2016). This indicates that multiple species in new ponds perform similar roles,
372 indicating functional redundancy (Lawton & Brown, 1993). Hence, macroinvertebrate taxa in
373 new ponds possess similar trait combinations and did not occupy the functional space as
374 efficiently as those in reference sites (Mason et al., 2005).

375 In general, the functional diversity of communities is driven by stochastic (i.e.,
376 dispersal) and deterministic (environmental and biotic filtering) processes, which shift from
377 one to the other during succession (Pursche et al., 2013). Trait convergence results from
378 strong environmental filtering early after restoration i.e., abiotic conditions select for species
379 according to their tolerance, filtering suitable traits (Helsen et al., 2012), and functional
380 redundancy is likely across environmentally similar sites (Leibold and Chase, 2018).

381 However, the trait convergence found in this study was mainly related to dispersal related
382 traits affecting the capacity to colonize new habitats (e.g. aerial dispersal, flier, winged
383 organisms). Dispersal is expected to be high in early colonizers common in new ponds, such
384 as Coleoptera and Hemiptera (which have 1 pair of wings+psuedoelytra), which are fast
385 colonizers (Ruhí et al., 2013) that establish rapidly and persist (Fairchild et al., 2000). In
386 contrast, the greater association between species that lack wings (low propensity to dispersal;
387 e.g. Crustacea and Gasteropoda) or possess two pairs (e.g., Odonata) and are predators with
388 reference sites, reflects their greater maturity and structural complexity (Coccia et al., 2016),
389 providing more oviposition sites and prey. Other studies elsewhere showed predominance of
390 high dispersal taxa in new restored ponds (Barnes, 1983; Ruhi et al., 2013; Kim et al., 2014;
391 Lu et al., 2021). Our initial predictions were supported and, although communities in both
392 wetland types are largely re-assembled through colonization from nearby permanent
393 wetlands, new ponds are dominated by early colonizers, whose movement from one new pond
394 to another could be enhanced either by their sub-optimal homogeneous environmental
395 conditions or their spatial configuration. From a functional perspective, this suggests that the
396 restoration remains in a pioneering phase, as expected since these are temporary wetlands,
397 and given previous studies showing the functional recovery of macroinvertebrate
398 communities takes a long time (Moreno_Mateos et al., 2012; Español et al., 2015).

399

400 *Patterns of functional beta diversity*

401 Contrary to our expectations, the individual contribution of new ponds and reference sites to
402 the regional functional beta diversity was similar. Nevertheless, reference sites contributed
403 more to regional functional turnover, whereas new ponds contributed more to regional
404 functional nestedness, even though they possess similar levels of multivariate functional
405 dispersion. The lower contribution of new ponds to regional functional turnover suggests less

406 functional replacement than in reference sites. This may reflect the greater functional
407 redundancy in their communities (Baiser & Lockwood; 2011) probably as result of a lower
408 diversity of microhabitats compared to reference sites, which held the highest proportions of
409 unique sets of traits

410 Moreover, the higher contribution of new ponds to regional functional nestedness,
411 particularly during the second hydroperiod, suggests that macroinvertebrate communities in
412 some new ponds present a subset of traits from more functionally diverse reference sites. This
413 result contrasts with the previous study based on taxonomic diversity (Coccia et al., 2016), in
414 which we showed that new ponds were not impoverished taxonomic subsets of reference
415 sites. While, mismatches between taxonomic and functional composition patterns have been
416 reported in both terrestrial and aquatic taxa, including macroinvertebrates (Bevilacqua &
417 Terlizzi, 2020), as result of different processes operating on the multiple facets of
418 biodiversity, the elimination of some taxa from this study may also play a role in explaining
419 the observed differences. On the other hand, findings for functional macroinvertebrate
420 diversity do not generally apply to other taxonomic groups, since they are not good surrogates
421 e.g. for vertebrate communities (Guareschi et al. 2015). Neither do such functional results
422 indicate value for specialized species, which may benefit e.g. from low connectivity (Pander
423 et al. 2018).

424 Importantly, May communities in these Mediterranean wetlands consist mostly of
425 macroinvertebrates that lack resistant stages to survive the long, dry summer and recolonized
426 these sites each year. In such colonization-dominated systems, significant levels of nestedness
427 are not unusual (Ruhí et al., 2013), as strong dispersers that dominate pioneering communities
428 drive nested patterns (Florencio et al., 2011).

429 However, the varied contribution of functional nestedness and turnover across wetland
430 types and time suggests that colonization changed between years especially within new

431 ponds. There are several factors, not included in this study, that can drive colonization pattern
432 and processes. For example, intrinsic water body characteristics (e.g., water permanence) and
433 specific species landscape perceptions (Pires et al., 2019; Cunillera-Muntcusi et al., 2020),
434 may have changed according to the annual variability in the precipitation regime, while the
435 colonization by invasive species increased during the second studied year (e.g., *Trichocorixa*
436 *verticalis*, Coccia et al., 2016), perhaps accentuating the degree of nestedness in new ponds.
437 Further research is needed to investigate these factors and to assess if the functional
438 composition of new ponds will become more similar to that of reference sites over time, or if
439 it will differentiate.

440

441 *Processes affecting functional dissimilarities across the study area*

442 We found that spatial and environmental variables had weak power in explaining the
443 overall functional beta diversity between new ponds and reference sites. This result agrees
444 with previous studies revealing that functional beta diversity and its components were poorly,
445 but similarly predicted by environmental and spatial variables for aquatic macroinvertebrates
446 (Heino & Tolonen, 2017, Pérez-Rocha et al., 2018; Hill et al., 2019). However, we found a
447 relatively stronger spatial effect on functional turnover, whereas environmental variables
448 exerted a stronger control on functional nestedness. These differences could reflect the
449 different spatial extent of study areas (280, 170 and >100000 km² respectively in the above
450 studies, vs 27 km² in ours), as biodiversity patterns are scale dependent (Pérez-Rocha et al.,
451 2018).

452 Dissimilarities in functional composition between wetland types increased
453 continuously as geographic distances between them increased (Fig. 6) In general, strong
454 spatial control on aquatic community assembly, including those dominated by insects like
455 ours may indicate either dispersal limitation or mass effects (Mouquet and Loreau, 2003;

456 Heino & Perscharsky, 2014; Galvez et al., 2020), depending on the organisms' dispersal
457 abilities. Interestingly, wetlands that were closer to each other exhibited lower functional
458 turnover, which increased as the distances among them increased (Fig. 6).

459 Spatially close wetlands tend to be more similar environmentally, biologically and
460 functionally (Leibold and Chase, 2018). Since this study included taxa with different dispersal
461 abilities, over short distances species with similar functional traits likely replaced each other
462 among adjacent new ponds and reference sites, producing low functional turnover between
463 them (i.e., homogenization by dispersal). In contrast, incomplete colonization and/or limited
464 dispersal across distant ponds and reference sites, which can occur even for stronger
465 dispersers (Galvez et al., 2020), could have increased dissimilarities in the functional
466 composition between them. However, it remains possible that the significant spatial effect
467 found in this study results from spatially structured environmental variables that were not
468 measured (Legendre et al., 2005).

469 Environmental variables significantly explained both regional functional beta diversity
470 and its components. Turbidity, fish, nutrient enrichment, pH and emergent vegetation were the
471 most relevant predictors (Fig. 6). All these variables are known to affect macroinvertebrate
472 assemblages and functions (Pérez-Rocha et al., 2018; Forio et al., 2018; Swartz et al., 2018;
473 Hill et al., 2019) and some of them also induced taxonomic nested patterns in aquatic
474 ecosystems (Gianuca et al., 2017). New ponds showed turbidity values below the threshold
475 where most functional changes occur (Fig. 6), contrary to the most isolated reference sites
476 (i.e., Entremuros 1 and 2, Caño and Rosaliman, see Fig. 1) well above this threshold (Coccia
477 et al., 2016). In addition, fishes were detected in a lower proportion of new ponds than in
478 reference sites (Table S4), and macroinvertebrate communities tend to be more dissimilar in
479 functional composition when fish are present. It seems that new ponds provide a refuge for
480 macroinvertebrates against the strong effects of fish predation and/or perturbation (Maceda-

481 Veiga et al., 2017), supporting communities that are functionally different from those in
482 reference sites.

483 However, new ponds also possess lower vegetation presence and showed pH and
484 nitrogen concentration values above the thresholds driving nested patterns (Table S4). Since
485 nestedness can result from differences in environmental tolerance among species (Driscoll et
486 al., 2008), some sets of functional traits related to environmental heterogeneity and sensitivity
487 to stressors have likely not yet been established in new ponds, producing assemblages with a
488 nested subset of traits from reference sites.

489 On the other hand, different variables were important in each hydroperiod. Even small
490 variations in hydroperiod length may change macroinvertebrate communities (Jeffries et al.,
491 2016; Pires et al., 2021), and the time and frequency of inundation changed between years in
492 our study system (Coccia et al., 2016).

493 *Management and restoration recommendation*

494
495 Our study identified several factors and process affecting the recovery of
496 macroinvertebrate functional diversity in restored ponds. First of all, we found that their
497 spatial arrangement (varying degree of distances between ponds and reference sites)
498 influences the dispersal dynamics between them, and in turn the set of traits they can support.
499 Then, we showed that both water quality (pH and nutrients) and habitat features (vegetation)
500 can constrain the recovery of macroinvertebrate functional diversity by limiting their spatial
501 distribution.

502 Wetlands are subjected to dynamic changes that can modify landscape characteristics
503 (e.g., connectivity), and in turn how species move between sites. Indeed, responses to
504 connectivity are taxon specific i.e., a high degree of connectivity may favor some species, but
505 it can be detrimental for others (Pander et al. 2018). Wetland dynamics in the Mediterranean

506 area will be further affected by climate change through salinization and interactions between
507 local stressors and higher temperatures (Green et al., 2017). Thus, appropriate wetland
508 restorations should: 1) consider spatial and temporal landscape dynamics (e.g., through
509 remote sensing) to predict possible desirable/undesirable restoration trajectories; 2) use a trait-
510 based approach to identify generalities across taxa dynamics respect to connectivity, major
511 stressors and their interactions, so as to know the implications of management and
512 conservation strategies; lastly 3) include specific actions such as transplanting or reseeded
513 helophyte vegetation. This is because helophyte vegetation can help trapping excessive
514 nutrient inputs that occur during heavy rainfall events, improving water quality (Paredes et al.,
515 2021) and increasing habitat heterogeneity.

516

517 CONCLUSIONS

518 New ponds are less functionally diverse than reference ponds, reflecting the dominance of
519 pioneering species, but their contribution to the overall functional beta diversity was similar to
520 reference sites, even though each contributed more to one component of beta diversity.
521 Environmental filtering and dispersal limitation are key drivers of changes in functional
522 composition between new ponds and reference sites, but their importance changed between
523 beta components. All together, we showed that new ponds did not reach functional
524 equivalency to natural wetlands within 7 years from restoration. However, their spatial
525 configuration and environmental characteristics allows them to support a different functional
526 composition to reference sites. Nonetheless, their contribution to the regional functional
527 diversity is mostly due to trait losses from reference sites driven by environmental filtering.
528 Therefore, specific restoration actions, such as transplanting or reseeded vegetation should be
529 made to improve their environmental conditions, and in turn the recovery of different sets of
530 functional traits.

531 We showed that the evidence-based approach used here reveals different and
532 complementary insights from taxonomy even over short time frame. However, both
533 taxonomic and functional diversity underpin ecosystem functioning and services, so that post-
534 monitoring studies should be more holistic.

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539 **AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS**

540 C.C., B.A.A., A.J.G. and J.A.C. conceived the study; C.C. J.A.C. and A.B.G collected the
541 data; B.A.A. analysed the data; C.C. led the writing of the manuscript. All authors contributed
542 critically to the drafts and gave final approval for publication

543

544

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551 Cayetano Gutiérrez-Cánovas for help with the trait dataset.

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553 **Data accessibility**

554 All data supporting this study will be openly available from Dryad.

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TABLES

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Table 1. Explained deviance and p-values from final Generalized Dissimilarity Models (GDMs) of regional beta diversity, and information on their selected variables. Variable importance is measured as the percent change in deviance between the full model and a model fit with that variable permuted.

	Explained deviance	Model p-value	Selected variables	Variable importance	Variable significance	Fitted permutations
2010						
Total Beta	-	-	-	-	-	-
Turnover	-	-	-	-	-	-
Nestedness	21.65%	0.007	Geograph. distance	0%	0.006	967
			Emergent vegetation	36.1%	0.016	995
			Total nitrogen	35%	0.006	999
2011						
Total Beta	24.1%	<0.001	Geograph. distance	39.7%	0.001	938
			Turbidity	52%	0.009	999
Turnover	27.4%	<0.001	Geograph. distance	4.5%	<0.001	986
			Nearest pond	10.8%	0.025	999
			Nearest reference	50.2%	0.005	999
Nestedness	6.5%	0.044	Geograph. distance	0%	0.038	909
			pH	94.6%	0.033	999

FIGURES

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801 **Figure 1** Map of the sampling sites in Doñana National Park. (A) Location of Doñana
802 within Spain, (B) study area in Doñana, (C) Reference sites (blue stars) and new ponds
803 (red circles), (D) close-up of the new ponds.

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821 **Figure 2** Representation of the alpha and beta functional diversity aspects used in this
 822 study in the functional space constructed for each scale. A) FRic: Functional richness;
 823 B) FEve: Functional evenness; C) FDiv: Functional divergence; D) FDis: Functional
 824 dispersion. Beta diversity functional spaces were built separately for total beta diversity
 825 and its turnover and nestedness components, and in two manners: E) to compare the
 826 contributions of each wetland type to overall beta diversity, and F) to compare beta
 827 diversity when calculated separately for each wetland type.

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834 **Figure 3** Violin plots of alpha functional diversity indices (mean \pm SE) by wetland

835 type. Letters indicate significant differences between types according to linear mixed

836 models. The functional space used to calculate all indices was built from the total pool

837 of species.

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849 **Figure 4** Violin plots of the raw Community Weighted Means values (mean \pm SE)
 850 according to wetland type. CWMs are only shown for which linear mixed models
 851 indicated a significant difference between wetland types. “Aerial active” (Dispersal
 852 trait); “flier” (Locomotion and Substrate Relation trait); “one pair of wings plus one pair
 853 of elytre/pseudoelytre” (Wing Pair Types trait); “predators” (Feeding Habit trait), “no
 854 wings”, and “two pairs of wings” (Wing Pair Types trait).

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868 **Figure 5** Violin plots showing the distances (mean \pm SE) of each wetland type to the
 869 median of all sites (new ponds and reference sites combined) in the multivariate space
 870 for functional beta diversity and its two components in each year and pond type. These
 871 values represent the contribution of each wetland type to regional beta diversity (and
 872 regional turnover and nestedness). Letters indicate significant differences between types
 873 according to linear models.

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880 **Figure 6** Multivariate dispersion analyses showing the distances between each reference
 881 site to the median position for all reference sites (green lines), and between each new
 882 pond and the median position for all new ponds (blue lines) for total beta diversity,
 883 turnover and nestedness during each year.

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890 **Figure 7** Partial regression fits of geographical distance and selected environmental
891 variables as predictors of total functional beta diversity (green line), turnover (blue line)
892 and nestedness (orange line) for reference and restored sites combined in 2010 (dashed
893 line) and 2011 (solid line). The steeper the slope of the line, the greater the predicted
894 beta diversity (or turnover/nestedness) on that section of the gradient. Geo. Dist.:
895 geographic distance; EmerVeg: emergent vegetation presence; Near pond: nearest new
896 pond; Near ref: nearest reference.

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